

NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING OF CRACKED METALLIC AIRCRAFT STRUCTURAL PANELS REPAIRED WITH A BONDED FRP COMPOSITE PATCH

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SUMMARY: Repair of cracked metallic aircraft structural panels using bonded FRP composite patches has been recognized as an efficient and cost-effective method to extend the service life of aging aircraft. In recent years, structural health monitoring of cracked metallic aircraft structural panels repaired with a bonded FRP composite patch has received wide attention. In this paper is proposed the method for identifying the shape of a crack in metallic aircraft structural panels repaired with a bonded FRP composite patch by utilizing the measured values of induced in-plane strains in the FRP composite patch under cyclic tensile loading. For several examples of crack shape, effects of number of strain measurement points and position of strain measurement plane in the bonded FRP composite patch on the identification results are examined. Moreover, effect of measurement error of strains on the identification results is also examined. The validity of the present method is found by comparing the identification results with the exact ones. Finally, for the identified crack, the ranges of stress intensity factor along the crack front and the growth rates of the crack under cyclic tensile loading are obtained.

KEYWORDS: patch repair, cracked metallic aircraft structural panel, FRP composite patch, identification of crack shape, strain measurement, growth rate of crack, structural health monitoring

INTRODUCTION

Repair of cracked metallic aircraft structural panels using bonded FRP composite patches has been successfully demonstrated [1-3]. In recent years, structural health monitoring of cracked metallic aircraft structural panels repaired with a bonded FRP composite patch has received wide attention, since it provides an indication of the integrity of the repair. Baker [4] suggested that a smart patch using in situ structural health monitoring may be necessary to alleviate certification concerns. By making numerical studies, Chiu *et al.* [5] reported the possibilities of using piezoceramics to detect a disbond of bonded FRP composite patch, and Koh *et al.* [6] performed the experimental work to validate the numerical studies [5]. The use of optical fiber sensors to monitor the integrity of the repair was also examined by McKenzie *et al.* [7] and Jones and Galea [8].

In this paper is proposed the identification method of shape of a crack in metallic aircraft structural panels repaired with a bonded FRP composite patch by using the measured values of induced in-plane strains in the FRP composite patch under cyclic tensile loading. In order to verify the validity of the method, effects of number of strain measurement points, position of strain measurement plane in the bonded FRP composite patch and measurement error of strains on the identification results are examined. Moreover, for the identified crack, the ranges of crack tip stress intensity factor and the growth rates of the crack under cyclic tensile loading are obtained.

IDENTIFICATION METHOD OF CRACK SHAPE

A cracked rectangular aircraft structural panel repaired with a bonded rectangular FRP composite patch subjected to cyclic tensile loading is depicted in Fig. 1. The crack is located at the center of the panel, and a FRP composite patch is bonded to the panel over the crack. A narrow elliptical disbond with minor axis of length d exists at the intersection of the crack and the bonded interface between the FRP composite patch and the panel. On a strain measurement plane in the FRP composite patch, the induced in-plane strains are measured at multi-points. The lengths of the cracked panel and FRP composite patch are $2L_p$ and $2L_r$, respectively. They have the same widths of $2W$. The thicknesses of the cracked panel and FRP composite patch are t_p and t_r . The panel is subjected to cyclic tensile stress with an amplitude $\Delta\sigma_0$ at $y=\pm L_p$.

The fracture surfaces of a cracked metallic aircraft structural panel subjected to cyclic tensile loading were observed by light microscopy. Figure 2 shows a micrograph of a typical example of the fracture surface. It is recognized from the figure that the crack front is curved through the thickness of the panel and the crack shape is characterized to be convex. Considering this fact, in the identification method, the crack front is assumed to be represented by a quadric function $a(z)$ of z , as follows

$$a(z) = \alpha_1 z^2 + \alpha_2 z + \alpha_3 \quad (0 \leq z \leq t_p) \quad (1)$$

where

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{1}{t_p} (2x_1 - 4x_2 + 2x_3), \quad \alpha_2 = \frac{1}{t_p^2} (-3x_1 + 4x_2 - x_3), \quad \alpha_3 = x_1 \quad (2)$$

Here, x_1 , x_2 , x_3 are the x -coordinate of the crack front at the free surface, mid-plane and bonded interface of the panel, respectively, as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 1 A cracked rectangular metallic aircraft structural panel repaired with a bonded FRP composite patch

Fig. 2 Micrograph of fracture surface of a cracked metallic aircraft structural panel subjected to cyclic tensile loading

Fig. 3 Crack shape

In the identification method of shape of a crack in the rectangular metallic aircraft structural panel repaired with a bonded rectangular FRP composite patch, the crack front is determined by minimizing the residual of normalized values of in-plane strain ranges $\Delta\varepsilon_i$, i.e. $\Delta\varepsilon_{xx}$, $\Delta\varepsilon_{yy}$, $\Delta\varepsilon_{xy}$, at multi-points in the FRP composite patch, which are induced under cyclic tensile stress with the amplitude $\Delta\sigma_0$. Then, the following optimization problem is set up.

$$\text{Minimize: } \sum_{i=1}^L \left\{ \frac{\Delta\varepsilon_i^m}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^L (\Delta\varepsilon_j^m)^2}} - \frac{\Delta\varepsilon_i^c}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^L (\Delta\varepsilon_j^c)^2}} \right\}^2 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Subject to: } x_1 + x_3 - 2x_2 \leq 0 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Design variables: } x_1, x_2, x_3 \quad (5)$$

Here, the superscripts m and c are referred to the measured and calculated values, respectively, and L is the number of in-plane strain ranges. The calculated values are obtained through an elastic FEM analysis. Eqn. 4 expresses the convexity condition of crack shape. The optimization is carried out using the feasible direction method with the bounded polynomial interpolation. We take $x_{10}=x_{20}=x_{30}=x_0$ as the initial values of design variables.

In the optimization problem, there are extremely many local optima. This means that we need to take the appropriate initial values of design variables to obtain the global optimum. In this study, we find the appropriate initial values of design variables by changing iteratively the initial values of design variables on the basis of the concept of the golden section method.

It is worthwhile noting that the in-plane strain ranges $\Delta\varepsilon_i$ would be independent of the process-induced residual stresses and the residual stresses due to temperature change in the FRP composite patch, and therefore we could ignore the residual stresses in the elastic FEM analysis. Furthermore, it

should be noted that the normalized in-plane strain ranges are independent of the amplitude of cyclic tensile stress in the elastic FEM analysis.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

The repaired metallic aircraft structural panel and the FRP composite patch in numerical examples are a 2024-T3 aluminum panel and a $[0_3/\pm 45/0_3/\pm 45/0_2]_s$ glass/epoxy laminate. The fiber direction of 0° is parallel to the direction of the cyclic loading. The dimensions and material properties of the panel and FRP composite patch are given as follows.

- (a) Metallic aircraft structural panel: $L_p=100\text{mm}$, $W=50\text{mm}$, $t_p=4.5\text{mm}$; $E=72.4\text{GPa}$, $\nu=0.33$.
- (b) Lamina of FRP composite patch: $L_r=25\text{mm}$, $W=50\text{mm}$, $t_r=0.23\text{mm}$; $E_{11}=44.1\text{GPa}$, $E_{22}=9.65\text{GPa}$, $G_{12}=4.13\text{GPa}$, $\nu_{12}=0.36$.

In the numerical examples, the minor axis of the narrow elliptical disbond is taken as $d=2\text{mm}$. As the measured in-plane strain ranges $\Delta\varepsilon_i^m$ at the multi-points on the strain measurement plane in the bonded FRP composite patch, the exact in-plane strain ranges $\Delta\varepsilon_i^{EXACT}$ calculated by an elastic FEM analysis are adopted for the case of no measurement error of strains. On the other hand, when we consider the effect of measurement error of strains, the following measured in-plane strain ranges are used:

$$\Delta\varepsilon_i^m = \Delta\varepsilon_i^{EXACT} \left(1 + \frac{S}{100} \times R \right) \quad (6)$$

where S is a value which indicate the maximum error and R is the uniform random numbers in the range from -1 to 1.

For the crack shapes, the cases of the following three crack fronts were examined.

$$\text{Crack front 1 : } a^{EXACT}(z) = -5.00 \times 10^{-2} z^2 + 2.25 \times 10^{-1} z + 14.7, \quad 0 \leq z \leq 4.5 \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Crack front 2 : } a^{EXACT}(z) = -8.00 \times 10^{-2} z^2 + 25.0, \quad 0 \leq z \leq 4.5 \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Crack front 3 : } a^{EXACT}(z) = -1.50 \times 10^{-1} z^2 - 1.50 \times 10^{-1} z + 34.9, \quad 0 \leq z \leq 4.5 \quad (9)$$

IDENTIFICATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effects of number of strain measurement points and position of strain measurement plane in the bonded FRP composite patch on the identification results of crack shapes are examined. Figure 4 shows the configurations of strain measurement points. The positions of the strain measurement plane are of free surface, mid-plane and bonded interface of the bonded FRP composite patch. In order to indicate the accuracy of the identification results, the error of the identification results of crack shape is evaluated by using the following formula:

$$\bar{a}_{ERROR} = \frac{1}{t_p} \int_0^{t_p} |a(z) - a^{EXACT}(z)| dz \quad (10)$$

The identification results in the case of no measurement error of strains are shown in Fig. 5. In the figure, the error of the identification results of crack shape is also indicated. It is seen from Fig. 5 that in the cases of 72 and 8 strain measurement points on a quarter of strain measurement plane, there are the identification results with more than $\bar{a}_{ERROR}=3(\text{mm})$, while in the case of 18 strain measurement points the identification results agree well with the exact ones. This might imply that we can not

Fig. 4 Configuration of strain measurement points on a quarter of strain measurement plane

obtain the effective identification results in the case of too many or too few strain measurement points and there is an optimal number of strain measurement points. Also, as can be seen from Fig. 5 (b), the best fit identification result is obtained when the position of the strain measurement plane is of the bonded interface of the bonded FRP composite patch. Figure 6 shows the effect of measurement error of strains on the identification results of crack shape. Here, we consider the case of 18 strain measurement points on a quarter of strain measurement plane and the position of the strain measurement plane being of the bonded interface. It is found from Fig. 6 that for the measurement error of strains of 2%, the errors of the identification results \bar{a}_{ERROR} are within 1mm. From this fact, the effect of measurement error of strains on the identification results of crack shape is a little when the measurement error of strains is within 2%.

Finally, for the measurement error of strains of 2%, the ranges of stress intensity factor ΔK along the crack front of the identified crack are obtained and the growth rate along the crack front is evaluated on the basis of following Paris relation:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C(\Delta K)^n \quad (11)$$

where N is the number of cycles, and C and n are material constants of the 2024-T3 aluminum, whose values are $C=7.04 \times 10^{-6} (\text{MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{1/2})^{-2.50} \text{mm/cycle}$ and $n=2.50$. The panel is subjected to cyclic tensile stress with the amplitude $\Delta\sigma_0=120\text{MPa}$. The ranges of stress intensity factor along the crack front and the growth rates along the crack front are shown in Fig. 7 and 8. The differences of the ranges of stress intensity factor and the growth rates between the identification results and the exact ones are small, even though the measurement error of strains of 2% is taken.

Fig. 5 Identification results of crack shape

Fig. 6 Effect of measurement error of strains on identification results of crack shape

(c) 8 strain measurement points

Fig. 5 (Continued) Identification results of crack shape

Fig. 7 Range of stress intensity factor along crack front

Fig. 8 Growth rate along crack front

CONCLUSIONS

We have proposed the identification method of shape of a crack in metallic aircraft structural panels repaired with a bonded FRP composite patch by using the measured values of induced in-plane strains in the FRP composite patch under cyclic tensile loading. Examination of the effects of number of strain measurement points, position of strain measurement plane in the bonded FRP composite patch and measurement error of strains on the identification results reveals that the effective identification results can not be obtained in the case of too many or too few strain measurement points and there might be an optimal number of strain measurement points. Moreover, the best fit identification result is obtained when the position of the strain measurement plane is of the bonded interface of the bonded FRP composite patch and the effect of measurement error of strains on the identification results of crack shape is a little when the measurement error of strains is within 2%. From these facts, the validity of the present method has been verified. Finally, it is certified that the differences of the ranges of stress intensity factor and the growth rates along the crack front between the identification results and the exact ones are small, even though the measurement error of strains of 2% is taken.

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REFERENCES

1. Jones, R., Davis, M., Callinan, R. J. and Mallinson, G. D., "Crack Patching: Analysis and Design", *J. Struct. Mech.*, 10, 177-190 (1982).
2. Baker A. A. and Jones R. (Editors), "Bonded Repair of Aircraft Structures", Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, Dordrecht, The Netherlands (1988).
3. Rastogi, N., Soni, S. R. and Denney, J. J., "Analysis of Bonded Composite Patch Repaired Metallic Structures: An Overview", *AIAA Paper*, 98-1883.

4. Baker, A., "Bonded composite repair of Fatigue-cracked Primary Aircraft Structure", *Composite Structures*, 47, 431-443 (1999).
5. Chiu, W. K., Galea, S. C., Koss, L. L. and Rajic, N., "Damage Detection in Bonded Repairs Using Piezoceramics", *Smart Mater. Struct.*, 9, 466-475 (2000).
6. Koh, Y. L., Rajic, N, Chiu, W. K. and Galea, S. C., "Smart Structure for Composite Repair", *Composite Structures*, 47, 745-752 (1999).
7. McKenzie, I., Jones, R. Marshall, I. H. and Galea, S., "Optical Fibre Sensors for Health Monitoring of Bonded Repairs", *Composite Structures*, 50, 405-416 (2000).
8. Jones, R. and Galea, S., "Health Monitoring of Composite Repairs and Joints Using Optical Fibres", *Composite Structures*, 58, 397-403 (2002).